

fertilizer than locally recommended NP rates and a 30-35% lower plant population. Modified 20- × 20-cm spacing could reduce up to 50% of the labor normally required for the UB placement by hand. Estimated VCRs for improved management of UB-DAP vis-a-vis the farmers' management ranged from 5.0 to 8.5. The VCRs for the conventional management of PU + SSP were less than 2.9 and economically unattractive. Stochastic dominance analysis indicated that the improved management of UB-DAP was a risk-free practice and therefore would be accepted by small farmers and preferred by policymakers. ■

Average rice yields under farmer-managed field trials as influenced by improved management of UB-DAP vis-a-vis the conventional and farmers' management of PU+SSP. Maharashtra State, India. 1993-95 wet seasons. ^a

Regime	Fertilizer	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
		Grain	Straw
<i>1993 wet season (n=26)</i>			
Improved	UB-DAP	4.6 ± 1.1 a	6.7 ± 2.3 a
Conventional	PU+SSP	3.0 ± 1.0 b	4.5 ± 1.9 b
Farmers'	PU+SSP	2.4 ± 1.1 c	4.1 ± 1.9 b
<i>1994 wet season (n=51)</i>			
Improved	UB-DAP	3.9 ± 1.1 a	5.3 ± 1.6 a
Conventional	PU+SSP	3.1 ± 1.0 b	4.4 ± 1.3 b
Farmers'	PU+SSP	2.7 ± 1.0 c	4.2 ± 1.3 b
<i>1995 wet season (n=40)</i>			
Improved	UB-DAP	4.1 ± 1.2 a	4.6 ± 1.2 a
Conventional	PU+SSP	3.0 ± 1.2 b	3.2 ± 1.3 b
Farmers'	PU+SSP	2.7 ± 1.1 b	3.2 ± 0.9 b

^an = number of field trials. Fertilizer rates used for the improved management of UB-DAP and the conventional management of PU and SSP: 56 kg N ha⁻¹+14 kg P ha⁻¹. Farmers' fertilizer rates varied and were lower than these rates. Av yields (± SD) for a given season followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other by LSD (P=0.05).

Effect of *Azolla caroliniana* and *Sesbania rostrata* on rice yield

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We studied how rice yield was affected with the use of *Azolla* as a dual crop and as green manure along with a green leaf manure plant, *S. rostrata*. Yield was compared using N fertilizer in pot culture. Experimental plots contained poorly drained fine soils occurring on the nearly level upper delta of the Ganges (Haplaquepts), pH 7.6; organic C, 0.58%; EC, 0.05 mmho cm⁻¹; N,

0.06%; 29.9 kg available P ha⁻¹; and 265.6 kg K ha⁻¹. *S. rostrata* was sown into the soil at 10 t ha⁻¹ just 1 d before transplanting. Nitrogen was 1.5% of fresh biomass. *Azolla caroliniana* was grown in a multiplication tank. As a dual crop, fresh *Azolla* was inoculated after 6 d of transplanting at 2 t ha⁻¹, left to grow along with rice, and incorporated into the soil after 20 d of growth. For basal application, fresh *Azolla* biomass at 10 t ha⁻¹ was incorporated into the soil 1 d before transplanting the rice.

In the presence of 15 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea, *Azolla* as basal/dual yielded much less than that of the control with

60 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea (see table). In the presence of 30 kg N as urea, *Azolla*-basal proves better compared with *Azolla*-dual. The use of *Azolla* as basal proved better compared with *Azolla*-dual. The use of *Azolla* as basal + dual was also better in the presence of 30 kg N as urea. The addition of *S. rostrata* as green manure (providing 60 kg N ha⁻¹) in the presence of *Azolla* (dual) almost negated the requirement of the addition of chemical N, whereas the addition of 30 kg N (as urea) to the above combination resulted in a significant 100% increase in the grain and straw yield over the control. ■

Effect of *Azolla caroliniana* and *Sesbania rostrata* on IR36 yield on the upper delta of the Ganges, India. 1994 wet season.

Treatment	N from urea (kg ha ⁻¹)	N from <i>Azolla</i> (basal) (kg ha ⁻¹)	N from <i>Azolla</i> (dual) (kg ha ⁻¹)	N from <i>S. rostrata</i> (kg ha ⁻¹)	Tillers at panicle initiation (no.)	Increase over control (%)	Grain yield (g)	Increase over control (%)	Straw yield (g)	Increase over control (%)
60 kg N (control)	60	—	—	—	8	—	13.7	—	11.5	—
15 kg N + <i>Azolla</i> (B) ^a	15	24	—	—	8	—	12.7	7.29	10.5	-8.69
15 kg N + <i>Azolla</i> (D) ^b	15	—	48	—	7	-12.5	9.5	-30.65	9.0	-21.73
15 kg N + <i>Azolla</i> (B+D)	15	24	48	—	8	—	12.5	-8.75	10.0	-0.13
30 kg N + <i>Azolla</i> (B)	30	24	—	—	8	—	14.0	2.18	15.0	30.43
30 kg N + <i>Azolla</i> (D)	30	—	48	—	8	—	13.0	-5.10	8.7	-24.34
30 kg N + <i>Azolla</i> (B+D)	30	24	48	—	9	12.5	14.2	3.65	12.2	6.08
No N + <i>S. rostrata</i> + <i>Azolla</i> (D)	—	—	48	60	15	87.5	22.5	64.23	24.5	113.04
15 kg N + <i>S. rostrata</i> + <i>Azolla</i> (D)	5	—	48	60	17	112.5	26.0	89.78	28.9	143.47
30 kg N + <i>S. rostrata</i> + <i>Azolla</i> (D)	30	—	48	60	17	112.5	27.0	97.08	29.5	186.53
CD (P=0.05)								6.74		

^aB = basal. ^bD = dual.